

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia: A Great Indian Freedom Fighter

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Abstract

This article attempts to explore the pioneer role of Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia in the history of Indian freedom struggle. Really, the 20th century was a very significant period in the history of modern India that the country witnessed the emergence of Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia, who devoted and dedicated himself to liberate our motherland from the bondage of the British. This article co-relates the warm bonds of Lohia with Gandhiji, and it is obvious that on his thought-process there were deep imprints of Gandhian concepts of non-violence, decentralization, Civil Disobedience and Satyagraha.

This article examines his contribution towards the Indian Freedom struggle in a great detail. At first, he organized a small 'Hartal' on the death of Lokmanya Bal Gangadhar Tilak. As a matter of fact, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia was introduced to the Indian Independence movement at an early age by his father through the various protest assemblies. Due to his nationalist approach, he wrote his Ph.D. thesis paper on the topic of 'Salt Satyagraha', focusing on Gandhian approach of Socio- economic theory to attain freedom. This article also explains his involvement in Indian National Congress. In May 1934, along with Jayaprakash Narayan, Acharya Narendra Deva and other prominent leaders he played a leading role in founding the Congress Socialist party (CSP). He made a series of caustic speeches urging Indians to boycott all Government Institutions.

This article highlights Lohia's active involvement in the Quit India movement of 1942 A.D. Even he had to change his name and fled to Nepal's dense jungles to evade the British. Lohia was captured in May 1944 A.D. and underwent extreme torture, but did not bow down to the British. As a true patriot, he always criticized the partition. His appeal to Hindu-Muslim Communities to stay united, ignore the violence and stick to Gandhiji's ideals of non-violence is the main objectives of his policies towards Indian National Movement. As a whole, this article illustrates the all-round characteristics of Lohia's active role in Indian National Struggle, in which he dreamt of a new dawn of freedom based on democracy, socialism, non-violence and disarmament & finally, we snatched freedom from the hands of the British on 15th August, 1947.

Key words :-

Satyagraha, Indian Nationalism, Nationalist approach, Salt Satyagraha, Quit India, Socialist, Boycott, Democracy, Disarmament, Freedom.

Introduction

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia was a great Indian freedom fighter, who fought with the British to make our Mother India free from the bondage of the British. As he was born in a small village named Akbarpur in Ambedkar Nagar district of Uttar Pradesh, his heart was filled with patriotic feelings, sacrifices and gratitude towards his own country. Really, the 20th century was a very significant period in the history of modern India that the country witnessed the emergence of this

veteran freedom fighter, who was born on 23rd march 1910 in a Marwari Maheswari family of Hira Lal Lohia and Chandri devi.

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia lost his loving mother when he was very young. Now he was deprived of the love and care of his mother. But he did not lose his heart, because he was a very courageous and bold from his early childhood. He learnt the patriotic lessons from his father. He was introduced to the Indian independence movement at an early age by his father through the various protest assemblies. His great contribution to the Indian freedom struggle was started by organising a small 'Hartal' (Strike) on the death of Lok Manya Bal Gangadhar Tilak. His father Hira Lal was an ardent follower of Mahatma Gandhi, who believed in the principles of 'Truth' and 'non-violence'. From his early childhood he learnt nationalist sentiments and fervour from his nationalist father. There is a saying in English 'Like father like son'. So was Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia, who was introduced to Mahatma Gandhi in a meeting by his father and that meeting deeply introduced Lohia and sustained him during trying circumstances and helped seed his thoughts, actions and love for swaraj.¹

Objective of the study

The objective of the present study is to critically analyse the position of Dr Ram Manohar Lohia as a *great Indian Freedom Fighter* in the pages of the annals of the Freedom Struggle of India & also to establish his role as a true patriot in attaining independence from the brutal hands of the British.

Methodology

The present study is completely analytical in nature. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data are taken from the various Government Reports, whereas the secondary source of data collection has been taken from the books, e-journal, articles & web-sites.

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia's role in the Freedom Struggle

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia joined a Satyagraha March at his tender age of ten to prove his allegiance to Gandhiji. As regards his educational background, he received primary education at Akbarpur, passed high school from Mumbai, intermediate from Varanasi and did Graduation in first division from Calcutta University. Due to his deep interests in debates and extra-curricular activities, he missed his first division in intermediate examination. In Varanasi he made wide reading of Hindi Literary texts and tried to understand Indian Philosophy and Polity. By the help of some Marwari Trusts he went to England for his higher studies. But he could not stay there for a longer period and went to Germany. While in Europe, Lohia attended the League of Nations assembly in Geneva, in which our country was represented by the Maharaja of Bikaner, an Ally

of the British Raj. This was the time when all Indians were enraged by the brutality of the British on salt Satyagrahis. The whole country witnessed the cruelty and barbarism of the British. On this occasion when he Maharaja of Bikaner was addressing the gatherings in the League of Nations, Lohia took exception to this and launched a protest then and there from the visitor's gallery.²

He fired several letters to the editors of news papers and magazines to clarify the reasons for his protest. The whole incident was full of patriotic feelings and made him a recognized figure in India over night. Lohia helped organize the 'Association of European Indians and become secretary of this club. His main motto was to attain Indian independence and for this very issue, he devoted and dedicated himself in the Indian freedom struggle. He is also known as the stormy petrel of Indian politics.

Due to his nationalist approach, he wrote his Ph.D thesis paper on the topic of 'salt satyagraha' focussing on Gandhian way of socio-economic theory to attain freedom under the guidance of late Professor Werner Sombart, a noted economist. He obtained his Ph.D degree from Humboldt (Berlin) university in 1932.³ Since his early student days, he was deeply influenced by the freedom struggle, Congress politics, student and youth Movements. In Germany, he wrote his Ph.D Thesis in German language also. During his stay in Mumbai and Kolkata, he developed command over Maratha and Bangla languages. The impact of his father, his academic background, the freedom struggle, participation in students movements, his polyglot character and close understanding of the socialist, communist and the Nazi movements in Germany--- played a crucial part in moulding the political orientations and influencing insights of Dr. Lohia.⁴

In 1933AD, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia came back to India and became an active member of Indian Freedom struggle. In May 1934 AD, along with JayaPrakash Narayan, Yusuf Mehar Ali, Minoo Masani, Sampurnananda and Achyut Patwardhan, Kamla Devi Chattpadhyaya, Ashok Mehta, S.M. Josi, Sane Guruji, Sibnath Banerjee and Abdul Bari, he played a very leading role in founding the Congress socialist party (CSP). From the very beginning, he was a member of its organizing and Executive Committees. He was appointed the Editor of the 'Congress socialist', English weekly of the party. In spite of scant resources, he turned this weekly into a powerful medium for raising national and international issues. When elected to the All India congress committee in 1936, Lohia formed a foreign affairs department for the first time. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru appointed him as the first secretary of the committee. During the two years that he served he helped to define 'What would be India's foreign policy.' Pandit Nehru called him a 'Rising Star' in Indian politics. Dr. Lohia brought out a regular AICC bulletin on foreign affairs and published several booklets related to foreign policy, India and China, war in Spain and Civil liberties. In one of the booklets of this period titled as 'Salient points of the Indian foreign policy', he laid the foundation of the foreign relations of the Indian National Congress which proved to be a precursor of Independent India's foreign policy. When the Second World War

broke out in Europe in September 1939, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia opposed the war efforts wholeheartedly, which was launched by the colonial administration in India. For his act, he was arrested and awarded a rigorous jail term. But, he didn't lose his courage, wisdom and hope. At that stage Gandhiji said, "I cannot sit still when I see Ram Manohar Lohia and JayaPrakash Narayan in jail. I do not know braver or straighter men than them". Since then, Gandhiji was especially fond of Dr. Lohia.⁵

On the onset of the Second World War, Lohia saw an opportunity to collapse the British Raj in India. He made a series of Caustic speeches urging Indians to boycott all Government Institutions. Though he was arrested on May 24, 1939, but released by authorities on the very next day in fear of a youth uprising. Soon after his release, On June 1, 1940 Lohia wrote an article called 'Satyagraha Now' in Gandhiji's Newspaper, Harijan. Within six days of the publication of the article, he was again arrested and sentenced to two years of jail. During his sentence the Magistrate said, "He (Lohia) is a top-Class scholar, civilized gentleman, has liberal ideology and high, moral character". Lohia was mentally tortured and interrogated by the jailors. In December 1941A.D. all the arrested congress leaders, including Lohia, were released in a desperate attempt by the government to stabilize India internally.⁶ He vigorously wrote articles to spread the message of toppling the British imperialist Government from countries in Asia and Africa. He also came up with a hypothetical blue-print for new Indian cities that could self administer themselves so well that there would not be need for the police or army.

Dr. Lohia's relation with Gandhi

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia had warm bonds with Gandhiji. We observe that on his thought-process there are deep imprints of Gandhian concepts of non-violence, Civil Disobedience and Satyagraha. In 1932 AD, the congress was banned and all the senior leaders were arrested. Great scholars and socialists like Acharaya Narendra Dev, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia, Ashok Mehta, Achyut Patwardhan were the main leaders of the Congress student party. The fact that only political freedom of India will not do freedom from hunger, poverty, social and economic exploitation also must be achieved, which became the sole aim of Congress.⁷ Thus, Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia's concept of freedom meant not only the political freedom, but also economic and social freedom. He wanted to see a society where everybody can be benefitted equally in each and every term, only then the real sense of freedom can be attained.

In 1942 AD., when, Mahatma Gandhi launched the 'Quit India movement', Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia was a moving spirit behind the Quit India's movement and a leading light along with Jaya Prakash Narayan, Achyut Patwardhan, Aruna Asaf Ali and Usha Mehta in organizing underground revolutionary Movement in 1942-44 AD. A fervent call was given by Gandhiji for 'Direct action' to force the imperialist British to quit India, the Gandhian call for 'Do or Die' was accepted by Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia. When the 'Quit India' struggle was launched, there were

for the first time prolonged strikes in industries in Coimbatore, Ahmadabad, Tatanagar and other places and the 'kisans'(farmers) overpowered the local administration, wherever possible. Parallel Governments run by the Congress revolutionaries were set up in the districts of Medinipur in Bengal, Bhoj Pur in Bihar, Ballia in UP and Satara in Maharashtra for weeks or Months. Socialists joined in the struggle whole heartedly and JayaPrakash Narayan, Lohia and Achyut Pattwardhana became the leaders of the underground revolt.⁸

'The three letters to the fighters of the freedom,' written by JayaPrakash Narayan and his colleagues also inspired hundreds of young persons to join it. The struggle brought the socialists under the influence of Gandhiji. On the issue of economic and social justice, Gandhiji too had moved much forward and favoured abolition of zamindari system and a low governed trusteeship of large industries, under social ownership. After this the struggle was launched by JayaPrakash Narayan, who was in Hazaribagh jail & escaped arresting from it on November 8, 1942 along with 5 other colleagues. They joined with Dr Ram Manohar Lohia who had escaped arresting from the beginning and they together organized the "Azad Dasta".⁹ Arrested in Nepal, but released by colleagues who led a jail break, they were ultimately arrested, though separately, in late 1943, and were kept in the Lahore central jail, where they were brutally tortured. After that, they were shifted to Agra Central Jail. On the other hand, the communists strongly opposed the struggle and supported the imperialists on the plea that they were doing so for the defence of the Soviet Union. The struggle made the socialists very popular, and Jayaprakash Narayan and Dr Ram Manohar Lohia became very prominent leaders of the Indian freedom struggle.

On the eve of 'Quit India movement' Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia printed and distributed many posters, pamphlets and bulletins on the theme of 'Do or Die' from his secret printing press. Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia along with freedom fighter Usha Mehta broadcast messages in Mumbai from a secret Radio Station called 'Congress Radio' for three before detection, as a measure to give the disarranged Indian population a sense of hope and spirit in absence of their leaders. He also edited 'Inquilab'(Revolution), a congress party monthly along with Aruna Asaf Ali. Afterwards, Lohia went to Kolkata to revive the movement there changed his name to hide from the police who were closing on him: Lohia fled to Nepal's dense jungles to evade the British. There he met, among other Nepalese revolutionaries, the Koirala brothers, who remained Lohia's allies for the rest of their lives.

Mino Masani, one of the associates of JP's Lohia writes, "When I got elected as a congress member of the Indian Legislative Assembly in September 1945, Jayaprakash Narayan was still detained in the Agra central prison along with Ram Manohar Lohia. My first speech in the Indian Legislative Assembly was a short one demanding J.P's and Lohia's release".¹⁰ In a letter from Agra prison on 8th March 1946, Jayaprakash Narayan said that he liked my speech, but he could not resist a critical comment. I had described J.P. and Lohia as great patriots.

Dr. Ran Manohar Lohia & his Azad Dasta

The story of “Azad Dastas” organized by Jayaprakash Narayan and Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia in the Terrai region on Indo-Nepal Border, their capture by the Nepalese police and their rescue from the lock-up by Suraj Narain Singh and his band after shorting the lock up guard is another chapter in JP- Lohia’s glorious record.¹¹ Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia and JayaPrakash Narayan were originally Marxists by persuasion and they believe in the theory of class-struggle propounded by Marx, Engles, Lenin or Mao.

After, coming into contact with the Gandhiji during the non-violent struggle for India’s Independence, they started mellowing down. Lohia remained a socialist until his unnatural death in 1967A.D. and he came to accept whole heartedly a few principles and programmes of Gandhian Sarvodaya. He believed in mass agitations and mass struggles. He was a champion of small kisans and landless labourers. But after 1942 AD he also came to believe in non-violence though unlike Gandhiji, it never became an inalienable part of his creed. Lohia was an indefatigable leader.¹²

Dr. Lohia’s emphasis on Constructive work

His main mission in life was the propagation of the ideology of democratic socialism and, if possible, capture the state power through the parliamentary programme, supported whenever necessary by non-violent direct action against all kinds of social, economic and political injustices. He was, therefore, engaged in incessantly fighting for justice freedom. He demanded preferential opportunities for the weak, oppressed backward section of Indian society, instead of mere equality of opportunities. Lohia, therefore, emphasized on *constructive work* among the masses. ‘The prison, the ballot and the ballot box’ was his three item formula for those who wanted to work for a democratic egalitarian social order. With a view to broadening the base of democracy as desired by Gandhiji, Lohia put forward his scheme of the “The four pillar state namely, the village (or the town), the district, the state and the centre. The four pillar state was obviously a scheme for the decentralization of the political power.¹³

Lohia was captured in May 1944 in Mumbai and he was taken to a notorious prison in Lahore, where it is alleged that he underwent extreme torture. His health was destroyed but even though he was never as fit his courage and will-power strengthened through the ordeal. Under Gandhiji’s pressure, the government released Lohia and his Comrade Jayaprakash Narayan. After release from jail, there was a new phase of struggle in Lohia’s life. In June 1946 A.D., he was arrested in Goa by the Portuguese administration where he had gone to take some rest after the gruesome jail term. That proved to be the harbinger of Goa’s struggle for independence. Gandhiji supported Lohia’s action and openly admired his steps; Dr. Lohia also supported the

movement launched by Nepali Congress against Rane Regime in Nepal from its beginning in 1946 A.D.

Dr. Lohia's views after attaining independence from the British

As India's tryst with freedom neared, Hindu- Muslim Strife increased, he strongly opposed Partitioning India in his speeches and writings. He appealed to communities in riot-torn regions to stay united, ignore the violence surrounding them and stick to Gandhiji's ideals of non-violence. It was due to his extra ordinary efficiency and capabilities that made us free from the bondage of the British. We snatched freedom from the hands of the British. On the 15th of August 1947, as the rest of India's leadership gathered in Delhi for the handover of power, Lohia stayed by Gandhiji's side as he mourned for the effects of partition.

As a matter of fact, we got freedom on 15th August 1947, but Dr.Ram Manohr Lohia was not happy enough to see the problems based on the language, caste, class, religion etc. So, he favoured Hindi as the official language of Hindustan. In Lohia's words , "The use of English is a hindrance to original thinking ,progenitor of inferiority feelings as a gap between the educated and uneducated public .Come, let us unite to restore Hindi to its original glory" Lohia decided to make the mass public realize the importance of economic robustness for the nation's future.

CONCLUSION:-

On the basis of above facts ,we can say that Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia was a man of action and a true Gandhian hero in leading powerful people's movement in the form of civil Disobedience Movement & Quit India Movement. As a nationalist, Lohia was a violent fighter of Indian Independence and his primary concern was to make India free from the bondage of the British. He started his freedom Movement in his tender age and throughout his life he fought bravely to see India as a country of his Ideals and principles. Truly speaking ,he was a champion of a new civilization based on democracy, socialism, non -violence and disarmament .On the occasion of his birth centenary ,let us resolve to reanalyze Lohia's intellectual contributions and whatever he dreamt of to see India's glory, we must work harder and harder to make all his dreams a reality .

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